

water was also taken through the whole process. The results are recorded in the Table.

TABLE: ESTIMATION OF THIOCYANATE, THIOUREA AND PHENYLTHIOUREA

Taken (mg)	Found (mg)	Error (mg)
	Thiocyanate	
2.18	2.18	0.00
2.72	2.72	0.00
3.26	3.25	-0.01
3.81	3.80	-0.01
4.35	4.35	0.00
4.89	4.88	-0.01
5.44	5.43	-0.01
	Thiourea	
2.85	2.85	0.00
3.56	3.55	-0.01
4.28	4.28	0.00
4.99	5.00	+0.01
5.70	5.72	+0.02
7.13	7.09	-0.04
	Phenylthiourea	
5.60	5.70	+0.10
7.00	6.97	-0.03
8.20	8.23	+0.03
9.40	9.0	+0.10
10.60	10.77	+0.17
11.40	11.40	0.00
12.80	12.86	+0.06

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to the authorities of Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra for providing research facilities.

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Synthesis of 1-(*p*-Carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-Trimethyl-2-Pyrazoline. Its Amides, Esters, Hydrazide, Benzylidenes and Thiosemicarbazid Derivatives

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Manuscript received 18 March 1978, accepted 10 June 1978

PYRAZOLINES were first reported by Knorr and Blank¹. 1 Phenyl pyrazoline was obtained by Fischer and Knoevenagel² from phenylhydrazine and acrolein, instead of the expected hydrazone. It was

found by v. Auwers and Voss³ that pyrazolines are formed when α, β unsaturated carbonyl compounds reacted with arylhydrazines. They also found that when the hydrazones were isolable, treatment with acetic acid caused rearrangement to the corresponding pyrazoline.

p-Carboxyphenylhydrazine has been used as a carbonyl reagent by Veibel⁴. He also found that α, β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds reacted with *p*-carboxyphenyl hydrazine to form 1-aryl-2-pyrazolines.

p-Carboxyphenylhydrazine reacted with mesityl oxide to give 1-(*p*-carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline (I).

IR ν_{max} Nujol: 1600, 1660, 2900-2960 cm^{-1} .

N.M.R. ($\text{CCl}_4 + \text{D}_2\text{O}$): δ 11.5, 7.98 $J = 8$ cps; δ 7.22, $J = 8$ cps; δ 2.82, 2.05 and 1.55.

The above values are in keeping with the structure assigned.

Experimental

1-(*p*-Carboxyphenyl)-3,5,5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline (I):

To *p*-carboxyphenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.1 mole), dissolved in 50% ethanol (150 ml) was added freshly distilled mesityl oxide (0.1 mole), and the

mixture refluxed for 4 hours. The mixture was then filtered into crushed ice and the acid obtained was purified by dissolving in sodium bicarbonate solution; filtering and acidifying the filtrate with 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid. White needles from 50% ethanol in 69% yield, m.p. 171°.

(Found: C, 67.27%; H, 7.3%; N, 11.98%; Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_2$: C, 67.22%; H, 6.94%; N, 12.06%).

The methyl and ethyl esters were prepared by the usual process of passing dry hydrogen chloride into a solution of the acid (I) in the corresponding alcohol and refluxing the mixture for 2 hours. Methyl ester m.p. 113°; ethyl ester m.p. 132° in quantitative yields.

Acid chloride(II) of 1-p-carboxyphenyl)-3, 5, 5-trimethyl-2-pyrazoline(I):

To the acid (I) (0.02 mole) was added thionyl chloride (0.04 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour. The excess thionyl chloride was removed under vacuum. The crude mass was purified by dissolving in benzene and shaking up with ice-cold water. The benzene layer was dried immediately with anhydrous sodium sulfate and on evaporation yielded the acid chloride(II). Crystallised from petroleum ether to give pale yellow plates, m.p. 182°.

The acid amide was prepared by passing dry ammonia gas into a solution of the acid chloride in benzene. Crystallised from 50% ethanol from 89% yield, m.p. 147°.

Preparation of Anilides and Esters of Acid (I):

To the acid chloride(II) was gradually added a chilled suspension of the amine or phenol (0.001 mole) in 5% sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml). The mixture was shaken for half an hour after which it was allowed to stand at R.T. for half an hour; filtered, washed with water and crystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE-1

No.	Amine used	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Aniline	106	75	$C_{19}H_{21}ON_3$
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	121	78	$C_{20}H_{23}ON_3$
3.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	112	73	$C_{20}H_{23}O_2N_3$
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	159	70	$C_{19}H_{19}ON_3Cl$
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	108	68	$C_{19}H_{19}ON_3Br$

TABLE-2

No.	Phenol used	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	1-Naphthol	96	65	$C_{22}H_{23}O_2N_3$
2.	2-Naphthol	168	70	$C_{23}H_{25}O_2N_3$
3.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	142	45	$C_{19}H_{19}O_4N_5$
4.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	205	52	$C_{19}H_{19}O_4N_5$

Preparation of the Hydrazide(III) of Acid (I):

To the methyl ester of acid (I) (0.001 mole) dissolved in methanol (5 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (3 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 14 hrs. After concentration and cooling, the hydrazide precipitated out. Pale yellow crystals from 20% methanol in 70% yield, m. p. 74°.

The *N*-benzylidene derivatives were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of the hydrazide and the aldehyde in methanol as solvent for 2 hours. Crystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE-3

No.	Aldehyde used	m.p °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Anisaldehyde	198	74	$C_{21}H_{24}O_2N_4$
2.	Salicylaldehyde	138	79	$C_{20}H_{22}O_3N_4$
3.	Furfuraldehyde	239	76	$C_{18}H_{20}O_3N_4$
4.	4-Hydroxy-benzaldehyde	212	65	$C_{20}H_{22}O_4N_4$
5.	5-Nitro-benzaldehyde	201	68	$C_{20}H_{19}O_5N_5$

The thiosemicarbazides (IV) were prepared by refluxing the hydrazide (0.0024 mole) in ethanol (6 ml) with the isothiocyanate (0.024 mole) for 2 hours. On cooling the reaction mixture, the thiosemicarbazides precipitated out. Crystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE-4

No.	Isothiocyanate used	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Phenyl	174	86	$C_{20}H_{23}ON_3S$
2.	4-Tolyl	194	82	$C_{21}H_{25}ON_3S$
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	165	87	$C_{20}H_{23}ON_3SCL$

Preparation of 3,4-disubstituted-5-mercapto triazoles:

The thiosemicarbazides (0.01 mole) was suspended in 2 *N* sodium hydroxide (5 ml) and refluxed for 1 hr. The solution was filtered and cooled. The filtrate, on acidification with acetic acid yielded the triazoles. Crystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE-5

No.	4-Substituent	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Phenyl	278	76	$C_{20}H_{21}N_5S$
2.	4 Tolyl	265	72	$C_{21}H_{23}N_5S$
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	261	75	$C_{20}H_{21}N_5SCL$

Preparation of 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles:

To concentrated sulfuric acid (10 ml) kept below 0° during addition and for 1 hr. more, was added in small quantities the thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mole). The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight, warmed to 50° and poured into crushed ice. The thiadiazole iprecipitated out. It was filtered, washed with dilute ammonia and water. Crystallised from 50% ethanol.

TABLE—6

No.	5-Substituent	m.p.°C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	Phenyl	190	57	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₃ S
2.	4-Tolyl	206	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₃ S
3.	4-Chlorophenyl	234	55	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₃ SCl

Note : All melting points are uncorrected.
All the compounds on analysis were found to correspond with the required values

Acknowledgement

Thanks to Ciba-Geigy Research Centre, Bombay, for all spectral and elemental analyses.

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Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species : Part VI : *Sonneratia apetala*

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Manuscript received 5 May 1978, revised 14 August 1978,
accepted 6 September 1978

LITERATURE survey¹⁻⁶ on the genus *Sonneratia* (Fam. Sonneratiaceae) reveals the presence of ellagic acid and its methyl ester ; anthraquinonoids derivatives ; gibberellin from its five species and ursolic acid and β -sitosterol from *S. apetala*. The present report on *S. apetala* from Sunderban area (Lat. 16° NH) and Kakinada area (Lat. 20° NH) is mainly intended to determine the ecological influence upon the plant on its secondary metabolites. The analysis confirms the presence of ursolic acid and β -sitosterol (in abundance) together with β -amyirin and taraxerol (in traces) in all the investigated species which were systematically collected in the month of December.

The finely powdered bark of *S. apetala* (7.0 Kg) from Sundarban area was extracted with petroleum for 30 hrs. The ether soluble portion of the extract was then separated into neutral and acidic fraction. The neutral fraction consisted of the following compounds (by column chromatography).

The first fraction, petroleum benzene eluate (5.0 lit., 7 : 3) yielded triacontanol m. p. 80° (0.25g)

Second fraction had m. p. 260° which on repeated crystallisation from benzene-ethanol mixture furnished a white crystalline compound (0.02g) m.p. 268°. The identity of this compound with that of taraxerol has been confirmed through mixed m.p., tlc., co-GLC study (Ret time ; 17 : 7 mins at 250-256.5°. Column material : 3% SE 30 on gas chrome-Z, 60-80 mesh).

Third fraction (benzene eluate, 3.0 lit.) furnished a mixture which was separated through fractional crystallisation from benzene-ethanol. The pure compound was identified as β -amyirin by mixed m.p. 195° and super impossible IR spectrum : $\nu_{\max}$ 3250 (hydroxyl), 1775 (double bond), 1450 and 1350 (gem dimethyl) cm⁻¹.

The last fraction contain large amount of β -sitosterol (3 g) m.p. 135° from benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate.

Acidic fraction (8.0 g) of each extract was esterified with ethereal solution of diazomethane. The crude ester (14.0 g) on chromatography over silica gel G (750 g) yielded a triterpenic ester which on repeated crystallisation from aqueous ethanol (80%) furnished homogeneous shining crystals (6.0 g) m.p. 110°. $[\alpha]_D +520$, $\nu_{\max}$ 3300 (-OH), 1720 (carbonyl), 1640 and 790 cm⁻¹ (double bond), derivative. Uvaol (LiAlH₄ reduced product of methyl ester) m.p. 218°. All these data confirmed the identity at the methyl ester with methyl ursolate.

S. apetala from Kakinada showed identical result.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly indebted to Mr. Asit Baran Sinha of the Department of Chemistry, Burdwan University for constant help during the whole programme of the present investigation.

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